

Paper 4

PREPARATION OF ENGINEERS FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Recent years it is evident that commercialization has huge impact on educational system; marketing strategies are used extensively when compared to before days. For the evolution of technology and applied science, it is crucial to consider quality in engineering education for any country. It is obvious that engineers have to work on changing technological demand for a sustainable future, need to keep track of changes and advancements in technology. For the accomplishment of quality in engineering education, universities and technical institutions should be proactive to the changing needs of the country. With the advancement of science and technology, the world we live has become small and it is essentially a knowledge-based society now. The major challenge now a day is teachers have to reach many learners as possible, everyone possesses different learning style and preferences. To satisfy these needs engineering programs has to alter their instruction methods, demands constant updating teaching and learning methods, more emphasis to be given on learning rather than teaching. With increased number of engineering institutions and number of graduates, one must not forget quality facets. Quality of engineering education can't be described in terms of product specifications as in case of industrial products. The TQM in education system will predominantly give fruitful results, and hence it has emerged as one of the important tools for ensuring improvement and sustainable quality in education. In this paper we did attempt to analyze the present condition of engineering education in India and also describe the quality management practices.

Approach: Applying Co-operative Learning Strategy and Total Quality Management in engineering education for improving the quality to meet the changing needs.

Findings: With the combined effort of instructors and students in creating a cooperative learning environment, students were able to gain leadership and decision-making skills, teamwork skills.

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TQM is proven methodology to increase quality with cost effectiveness.

Value: A cooperative learning strategy and application of TQM in engineering education is discussed for the sustainable future engineers.

Paper Type: Conceptual Research.

Keywords: Total Quality Management (TQM), Quality Assurance, Cooperative Learning, Cooperative Learning, PDCA Cycle.

1. INTRODUCTION:

For the past few years due the commercialization of education system, many new engineering universities and new programs were added, which significantly increase the number of students getting graduated every year, who are not tuneful to the needs of the labor market. As per government records, India has got 3500 engineering colleges, producing approximately One Million engineering graduates per year. The major question arises in everyone’s mind is ‘being all graduates, are skilled up for the labor market needs?’ Engineering education in India needs to be re-evaluated to adopt new quality policies. The term ‘Quality’ has attracted the attention of educationalist across the world since last few decades. The reason is like globalization of higher education, increasing the number of programs, augmentation of e-learning and multicultural workplace conditions [1].

The Quality Monitoring comprises of Quality enhancement and Quality assurance, but due to present pressure for accountability, the Quality assurance facet has gained higher importance than Quality enhancement. This leads all universities and colleges to engage themselves in Quality review, a process where they have to display the procedures and processes; they follow to ensure Quality for their students beyond the teaching and learning [2, 3].

The multidisciplinary and multicultural working condition demands major transformation in engineering education, it is found from many reports pointing out the huge gap between engineering education and practices. The UNESCO report highlighted lack of skills in graduated candidates and stressed on Project Based Learning [4].

As stated before, Quality assurance is widely sought due the external pressure for accountability. Though it has good reasons, it also leads to degrade the Quality of Teaching and Learning with adoption of industrial quality processes and the time faculties spend on the accreditation process distracts their attention from developing teaching and learning [5].

Due to the pandemic crisis, the online class pattern has been emerging demands many traditional teaching staffs to engage online classes. Many of such faculties lack formal education in how to successfully teach

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online, attention must be given in such cases to make sure that Quality is delivered [6 - 8].

2. Engineering Education in India Challenges and Opportunities:

India has got a leading number of engineering institutes, producing large number of engineers in the world. Every year, 1 million engineering graduates are produced, out of which roughly 10% students are graduating from national level autonomous institutes built and governed by the acts of parliament [9]. Rest 90% students are getting a graduation from a non – autonomous state level institution. With this diversified number of engineering institutes, quality across engineering education is a major challenge.

The regional disparities, a difference in engineering education service between different regions are clearly visible. For smooth and harmonious development of any county, a balanced regional development plays a vital role. It is observed that some regions of the country are having higher number of engineering institutions, whereas some regions are significantly less. Forbes reports regional disparity in the Indian Innovation ecosystem as well.

The program wise imbalance is spotted during recent years, new programs are added, and additional seats are created only for a narrow band program. Core branches of engineering programs are sidelined temporarily or permanently.

As semiconductors, robotics, artificial intelligence is advancing, India is also getting its involvement in new technologies and many multinationals are set to invest in India. This implies, an engineering student should be provided a good amount of opportunity to groom their skill sets using a brainstorming session, presentations, lectures with the assistance of technology [10]. The influence of economic globalization has brought tremendous positive impact of technology on present society which was never as predicted before, with these rapid advancements future engineers can be outlined as;

- a. Knowing everything, able to gather the information about anything in no time and know how to assess the information.
- b. Able to do any task, adapt to the changing requirements, learn new tools and use effectively.
- c. Work with anybody and anywhere, should have good communication skills, know to work in a team, able to understand global issues.
- d. Should have high imagination capability and make it into reality, should possess managerial skills to recognize the needs, put forward new methods to solve problems and work through.

3. Co-operative Learning Strategy:

A paradigm shift from traditional instruction-based teaching to the learning-based education is observed in the early 1990s by Robert Barr and John Tagg. In instruction-based learning it is being realized, most of the students are not able to stay focused for more than 30 minutes stretch, not able to absorb much [11].

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The students are divided into smaller teams, comprising of different levels of ability is a proven learning strategy for greater learning experience. On a team each member is expected to help teammates to learn, creating an achievement kind of environment.

‘What is the role of teacher in cooperative learning?’ is an important question to be asked and known, teacher’s involvement is crucial in the success of this model. The teacher must know to form a cooperative learning in teams, deciding the team size and preparing the framework of task sets. The teacher needs to monitor the process and its outcomes. The main element for the success of cooperative learning in classroom is identified as;

- a. Members of the team sharing common goals.
- b. Individual and group accountability.
- c. Encouraging interaction.
- d. Interpersonal and small group skill trainings.
- e. Group processing.

A faculty can use this type learning for any course material or assignment, a team can be formed comprising 2 to 6 students. The different classes of cooperative learning strategies are;

- a. Make students to depend on each other.
- b. Creating assignments which demands group solving.
- c. Laboratory or mini projects.
- d. Review works.

4. Total Quality Management in Engineering Education:

TQM is one of the emerging management philosophies for the education, it is widely accepted by industries and service sectors, and however its application to higher education is still controversial. TQMs focuses on customer orientation, which is against the nature of the education system, education institution often works independently of market affairs. Even though TQM poses certain problems in its application to higher education, it is not ruled out the need of change in this sector [12, 13].

There are a number of changes to be done by educational institution to adopt TQM, firstly attitude and activities of management towards monitoring of the education process, evaluation of its results, college atmosphere should be modified. The TQM in higher education has different viewpoints; it can be applied at 3 categories, (1) administrative and management strategies with improved efficiency, (2) teaching process with new methods and tools, (3) learning process improvements.

TQM focuses on the customer, identifying customers in higher education is to major challenge as compared to the other industries. Internal customers can be segregated as parents, students and staffs and external customers are society, future employers and other institutes where students continue their education. Most of

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the time administrator tends to believe students as customers, makes faculties to dislike being too commercial. Hence it is critical steps in the implementation of TQM in education, identifying current and potential customers.

Another essential element of TQM is involvement of all stakeholders in the process and management commitment to the changes. Next stage is to perform evaluation against set goals; the institution should set quality objectives and evaluate to prove improvements in attainment. Later step is continuous improvements; the TQM model should be reviewed and evaluated often on fixed intervals to make sure that goals are still focused. With the success of TQM in education the teacher’s part is very crucial, he/she has to be as a guide, facilitator enabling students to share knowledge, produce a quality work [14-17].

4.1 Plan-Do-Check-Act Procedure

For the control and continuous improvement of process in industry a PDCA model is widely used, it is an iterative design and management method. It is a 4 step; circle with no end, cycle is to be repeated continuously for improvement in quality. This procedure should be adopted starting new improvement process. Figure 1 indicates PDCA cycle structure, where; in planning stage set improvement objectives, tools and methodology; in Do stage implement the changes and perform some sort of study on improvements; in Check stage review the progress, perform analysis and identify what is being learnt; in Act stage take necessary action based on learning, if changes made did not yield and progress go through the cycle again with new plan.

Fig. 1: PDCA Cycle Procedure

4.2 Benefits of TQM in Engineering Education

TQM has proven track records in maintaining quality in higher education systems, not only improvements in quality it also offers increased quality at cost effective, improvement in overall productivity of all stakeholders, higher customer satisfaction which is the main element of TQM. In present scenario

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engineering students are expected to make a quick transition into the working environment, take part in a live project and changing technological needs, hence learning process has to be modified as per changing needs. The concept TQM has to be applied in engineering education in order to attain higher quality, education institutions are now a day treated as service providers; providing service to the students and the recruiting companies as well, in this concept TQM is more relevant for engineering education. It needs involvement of all stakeholders at all levels for its success.

5. Effective Teaching in Changing Education Circumstances:

Engineering universities are pressurized by both internal and external factors to improvise the quality of teaching and learning, and demonstrate the effectiveness of the process adopted [18 - 20]. Many researchers have made an attempt to describe what makes effective teaching skills and practices, to summarize;

- a. Student’s future needs must be considered while drafting curriculum and doing teaching, giving higher preferences to critical thinking, team work and interpersonal skills.
- b. No matter if the contents covered are reduced, but students must be given thorough fundamental knowledge.
- c. Relate the concepts taught to real life scenario.
- d. New methods should be used to engage students in learning process.
- e. Interactive environment must be created inside classroom and motivate students to participate.

6. Conclusion:

The science and technology are critical for the development of any nation; many advanced nations are known by their technological innovations. Keeping this point in mind, engineering education plays vital role in producing engineers and hence, development of technology and prosperity of the nation. The impact of technology on society is increased beyond the expected rate after the globalization of economy; the internet has created expanded market for products and services. Accountability has forced universities to focus on quality assurance rather than enhancement, TQM is emerged as a feasible solution for maintaining quality in engineering education to meet the global standards. A visionary administrator must make strong and consistent commitment towards development of their teachers/ instructors, enabling them to inspire, involve and transform even ordinary students into extra-ordinary.

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